

PLANNING THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA

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Joint Final Conference of SUPREME and SIMWESTMED

METHODS & TOOLS: Mixed Working Groups

Conclusions of the *Data and tools* working group

3 questions were addressed:

- Which are the fundamental data needed to deal with issues at a transboundary level?
- Are these data accessible, easily available?
- Which are the main gaps to address in a near future?

The data needed should be spatialized and include environmental data and socio-economic data. The priority data are bathymetry, boundaries, migratory routes, marine traffic, fishery and ecological data. Need to further integrate the MSFD directive and GES

The question of time is a priority issue particularly the update level and the future trends.

About accessibility, there is a need to ease the access at official data and scientific data.

One issue is the need to access the metadata and to standardize and harmonize datasets.

The accessibility raises the questions of data production process, business data, confidentiality and licenses.

Regarding the gaps and needs, the need is different according to the scale. The question of the interoperability of cross-border data is an issue that is managed at several scales: spatial scales and administration scales.

The data as a support to the policies requires the aggregation of data, the improvement of the representation (infographic) and the dissemination of the information.